

Rapid spectrophotometric determination of trace amounts of azorubine dye in food samples after dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction

Shahla Elhami* and Negar Noorzadi

Department of Chemistry, College of Science, Ahvaz Branch, Islamic Azad University, Ahvaz, Iran

E-mail : Sh.elhami@khouzestan.Srbiau.ac.ir

Manuscript received online 10 March 2015, accepted 14 June 2015

Abstract : A novel dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction method for the determination of azorubine by spectrophotometry has been developed. Azorubine is an anionic azo dye that was used in food industrial in some country. The method is based on the liquid-liquid microextraction of azorubine from aqueous solution using chloroform as extraction solvent and cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) as disperser and also as a cation for neutralization of azorubine. The effects of different parameters such as pH, type of extraction solvent, concentration of surfactant as dispersive solvent and time on the dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction of dye were investigated and optimum conditions were established. Under the optimum conditions the calibration graph was linear in the range of 10–1200 ppb with detection limit of 3 ppb. The relative standard deviation (RSD) for 50 and 1000 were 3.9 and 1.8% (n = 8), respectively. The method was applied to the determination of the azorubine dye in different food samples.

Keywords : Azorubine, cetyltrimethylammonium bromide, chloroform, dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction.

Introduction

Dyes are commonly added to industrial foods, and laws strictly control their uses. The maximum amounts allowed, and the acceptable daily intakes have been decreased. As these values differ for the various dyes, it appears necessary to identify and quantify with accuracy the dyes present in foods. Azorubine (Carmoisine, Food red 3 or E122 in Europe) is an artificial food additive that belongs to the azo dye class (Fig. 1). Azo dyes generally have been known to be carcinogenic for over 60 years and are linked, particularly, to bladder cancer. However azorubine itself has not been proven to be carcinogenic. It appears to cause allergic and/or intolerance reactions, particularly amongst those with an aspirin intolerance. Other reactions can include a rash similar to nettle rash and water retention. It is one of the colours that the Hy-

Fig. 1. Structure of azorubine dye.

peractive Children's Support Group recommends be eliminated from the diet of children. Azorubine is banned in Japan, Norway, Sweden and the United States¹.

Azorubine has been determined in different samples by several methods such as differential pulse polarography², thin-layer chromatography – “UV-Vis” spectrometry³, cloud point extraction⁴, fluorescence spectra⁵. However, there is still of interest to develop simple methods for the determination of azorubine in different samples.

Recently, a novel modality of the liquid-phase microextraction (LPME) technique is introduced. It is based on a ternary component solvent system as a high-performance and powerful preconcentration method, referred as dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction (DLLME)^{6,7}. DLLME has been successfully applied to the preconcentration of several families of organic⁸ and inorganic species⁹ in water samples. The advantages of the DLLME method are the operation simplicity, the rapidity, the low cost, the high recovery and the high values of the enrichment factors¹⁰.

The aim of this study was the development of a dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction method for the determination of azorubine. The method is based on extraction of

azorubine using chloroform as extraction solvent and cetyltrimethylammonium bromide as dispersive surfactant.

Experimental

Apparatus and materials :

In this research the following apparatus were employed : A spectrophotometry UV-Visible, manufactured by Varian, model : Carry 100, along with 350 μL quartz microcells; A pH meter, manufactured by Ohmeter, model : 750; A ELE centrifuge (Ieccentra-CLD).

All chemicals used were of analytical grade and doubled distilled water was used throughout. A stock solution of 1000 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ of azorubine was prepared by dissolving 0.100 g of the azorubine (Merck, Germany) in water and diluting to 100 ml in a volumetric flask.

Dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction procedure :

For DLLME under optimum conditions, an aliquot of the solution containing azorubine dye with a concentration of 10–1200 ppb and intended pH was prepared in a 10 mL volumetric flask. The solution was transferred to a glass test tube with a conical bottom. Two hundred microliters of chloroform (extraction solvent) containing 0.20 mM cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) which provides counter ion and also acts as a disperser was injected rapidly into a sample solution by using a 100- μL syringe (ILS, Germany) and then the mixture was gently shaken. A cloudy solution was formed in the centrifuge tube. The mixture was then centrifuged for 10 min at 3500 rpm. Then sedimented chloroform was removed using a 100 μL micro syringe and injected into the quartz microcell for analysis. The absorbance was measured at the wavelength of maximum absorbance of azorubine dye after extraction, 525 nm. A blank solution was also run using the entire mentioned components except azorubine dye.

Sample pre-treatment procedure :

Appropriate amounts of strawberry jelly, strawberry jelly powder, strawberry drink powder, watermelon jelly and watermelon beverage samples were dissolved in water, filtered if necessary and diluted to 25 mL in a volumetric flask. An aliquot of the above solutions was treated under the general procedure for dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction and subsequent determination of azorubine.

Results and discussion

A dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction methodology was developed for preconcentration and spectrophotometric determination of azorubine. The absorption spectrum of azorubine was recorded after dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction. It showed a maximum absorption band at 525 nm. Therefore, this wavelength was used for all the absorbance measurements. The effect of various dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction parameters such as pH, type of extraction solvent, concentration of surfactant as dispersive solvent and time on the performance of the method was investigated in order to achieve highest sensitivity.

The effect of pH :

The effect of pH on the dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction of 1000 ppb of azorubine was studied in the range of 1.5–6.0. Fig. 2 shows the influence of pH on the absorbance of the azorubine at 525 nm. As it is observed maximum absorbance is obtained at pH 3.5. At higher pH values, azorubine becomes colorless and its absorbance is decreased. Therefore, pH 3.5 was chosen for further work.

Fig. 2. Effect of pH on the absorbance of azorubine obtained from DLLME. Extraction conditions : concentration of azorubine : 1000 ppb, sample volume : 10 mL, injection 200 μL of chloroform (extraction solvent) containing cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (as disperser).

Selection of the extraction solvent :

The selection of a suitable extraction solvent is critical for the DLLME process. In the selection of the extraction solvent, certain properties of the solvent that need to be considered are : higher density than that of water, ability to extract analytes of interest, and low solubility in water. Based on these requirements, three different extraction

solvents including chloroform (CHCl_3), dichloroethane ($\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{Cl}_2$) and carbon tetrachloride (CCl_4) were selected. In order to choose the best solvent, a series of sample solutions containing 1000 ppb azorubine were studied using 400 μL , different solvents containing 0.10 mM CTAB. Chloroform has higher extraction efficiency than others. Therefore, chloroform was chosen as the extraction solvent in the experiment.

Effect of surfactant concentration in extraction solvent :

The concentration of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) was an important factor for achieving good extraction performance. CTAB was used as disperser and also as a cation for neutralization of azorubine because azorubine is an anionic dye. The influence of the CTAB concentration on the DLLME extraction of azorubine was evaluated in the concentration range of 0.05 to 0.50 mM, and the results are shown in Fig. 3. It can be seen that the absorbance of azorubine appeared to reach its maximum at 0.20 mM concentration of the surfactant. So, the 0.20 mM was selected as the optimum concentration of CTAB.

Fig. 3. Effect of CTAB concentration on the absorbance of azorubine obtained from DLLME. Extraction conditions : concentration of azorubine : 1000 ppb, sample volume : 10 mL, pH=3.5, injection 200 μL of chloroform (extraction solvent) containing cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (as disperser).

Effect of extraction solvent volume :

The volume of chloroform as extraction solvent has strong effect on the sensitivity due to its effect on enrichment factor. For this purpose a series of experiments were carried out with different volumes of chloroform (containing CTAB) in the range of 200–700 μL . As it is observed in Fig. 4, the absorbance of organic phase was decreased by increasing of the chloroform volume. This could be due to the dilution effect which decreases in concentration of the extracted species in sedimented phase. Using injection volumes less than 200 μL of chloroform

Fig. 4. Effect of solvent volume on the absorbance of azorubine obtained from DLLME. Extraction conditions : concentration of azorubine : 1000 ppb, sample volume : 10 mL, pH = 3.5, injection of chloroform (extraction solvent) containing 0.2 mM cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (as disperser).

(containing CTAB) lower volume of organic phase was obtained, so that the absorption signal could not be measured by spectrophotometer fitted with microcells. Thus, in order to achieve high enrichment factor and low detection limit value, 200 μL of chloroform was selected as optimum extractant solvent volume throughout the experiments.

Effect of extraction time :

In this experiment, extraction time was another parameter for DLLME. Extraction time is defined as interval between the injection of the mixture of disperser and extraction solvent (CHCl_3), and before centrifugation. Effect of extraction time was studied in the range of 1 to 20 min. According to the obtained results, the absorbance was not varied significantly. Thus, 2 min time was selected as an optimum time.

Interference studies :

The effect of potential interference of cations and anions on the DLLME and determination of azorubine using the proposed procedure was studied. An error of $\pm 5\%$ in the absorbance reading was considered tolerable. In these experiments, sample solutions containing of 100 ppb of the azorubine and different concentrations of other ions were treated under the recommended procedure using optimum conditions. The results given in Table 1 indicate that the method is selective for determination of azorubine.

Analytical figures of merit :

After optimization of all parameters, quantitative characteristics of the proposed method were studied. The linear dynamic range, correlation coefficient (r), repeatability, limit of detection (LOD) and preconcentration factor were determined to evaluate the method performance. The

Table 1. Tolerance limit of foreign ions

Interference	Interference/ Azorubine ratio
Pb ²⁺ , Cr ³⁺ , Cl ⁻ , SO ₄ ²⁻ , Ni ²⁺ , NO ₃ ⁻ , Zn ²⁺ , Na ⁺ , Co ²⁺ , Cr ₂ O ₄ ²⁻ , Ca ²⁺ , Cd ²⁺ , Ag ⁺ , Sr ²⁺	500
CO ₃ ²⁻ , K ⁺	250
Fe ³⁺ , Fe ²⁺ , Sn ²⁺	50

Table 2. Analytical characteristics of the presented DLLME method for determination of azorubine dye

Parameter analytical features	Parameter analytical features
Linear range (ppb)	10–1200
Correlation coefficient (<i>r</i>)	0.998
Detection limit (ppb) (3 δ , n = 10)	3
Precision (RSD % for 50 and 1000 ppb, n = 8)	3.9, 1.8
Preconcentration factor	50

analytical characteristics of the optimized method summarized in Table 2.

Application :

The proposed procedure has been applied to the determination of azorubine in different food samples. The results are given in Table 3. According to Table 3, the spiked concentration of azorubine can be quantitatively recovered from the food samples by the proposed procedure. These results demonstrate the applicability of the

Table 3. Determination of azorubine dye in real samples

Sample	Azorubine (ppb)		Recovery (%)
	Added	Found ^a	
Mineral water	0	ND	–
	100	104.0 ± 2.2	104.0
	200	206.1 ± 3.8	103.0
Strawberry jelly	0	321.0 ± 2.5	–
	100	417.2 ± 3.6	96.2
	200	511.1 ± 4.3	95.0
Strawberry jelly powder	0	260.0 ± 1.8	–
	100	363.0 ± 2.7	103.0
	200	460.1 ± 3.1	100.0
Strawberry drink powder	0	217.0 ± 1.2	–
	100	321.0 ± 2.1	104.0
	200	415.1 ± 2.9	99.0
Watermelon jelly	0	67.0 ± 0.9	–
	100	165.2 ± 1.4	98.2
	200	274.1 ± 2.0	103.5
Watermelon beverage	0	45.0 ± 0.4	–
	100	141.1 ± 1.2	96.1
	200	237.2 ± 1.9	96.1

^a $\bar{x} \pm ts\sqrt{n}$ at 95% confidence (*n* = 5).

procedure for dispersive liquid-phase microextraction of azorubine in food samples such as mineral water, jelly, drink powder, jelly powder and beverage.

Conclusion

In the present study a DLLME method has been employed for sensitive determination of azorubine. Miniaturization of toxic organic solvent using dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction combined with microvolume UV-Vis spectrophotometry allows the development of a green method which is environment-friendly. Besides simplicity of operation, rapidity, low sample volume, low cost and high enhancement factor are some advantages of the suggested method. Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) was used as disperser and also as a cation for neutralization of azorubine because azorubine is an anionic dye. A comparison between presented approach and previously reported method for the determination of azorubine is shown that the LOD and linear range of suggested method is better or comparable to the reported techniques^{2,4}. Furthermore the application of spectrophotometric detection has merits of simplicity, cheapness and portability. This methodology gives good accuracy, low limits of detection and excellent precision which show its potentiality in analysis of azorubine in food samples.

Acknowledgement

The authors wish to thank Khuzestan Science and Research Branch, Islamic Azad University, for financially supporting this study.

References

- "E122 Carmoisine", UK Food Guide, Retrieved 1 May, 2014.
- S. Combeau, M. Chatelut and O. Vittori, *Talanta*, 2014, **56**, 115.
- O. F. Marutoiu, I. Gogoasa, C. Marutoiu, M. Tofana, D. Moigradean and I. Gergen, *J. Agroal. Proce. Tech.*, 2011, **17**, 46.
- N. Pourreza and M. Ghomi, *Talanta*, 2011, **84**, 240.
- F. Kong, G. Chen, C. Zhu, R. Li, Y. Hu, Y. Zhang and Z. Zhu, *Spectrosc. Lett.*, 2014, in press.
- M. Rezaee, Y. Assadi, M. R. Milani Hosseini, E. Aghae, F. Ahmadi and S. Berijani, *J. Chromatogr. (A)*, 2006, **1116**, 1.
- N. Fattahi, S. Samadi, Y. Assadi and M. R. Milani Hosseini, *J. Chromatogr. (A)*, 2007, **1169**, 63.
- R. R. Kozani, Y. Assadi, F. Shemirani, M. R. Milani Hosseini and M. R. Jamali, *Talanta*, 2007, **72**, 387.
- G. Khayatian, S. S. Hosseini and S. Hassanpoor, *J. Iran. Chem. Soc.*, 2013, **10**, 1167.
- A. Bidari, P. Hemmatkhah, S. Jafarvan, M. R. Milani Hosseini and Y. Assadi, *Microchim. Acta*, 2008, **163**, 243.